

METHODOLOGY OF FORMING STUDENTS' WRITING SKILLS DURING PRIMARY CLASS LITERACY TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the main goal of teaching husnikhat is to teach the complex process of writing to young students, to develop their beautiful writing skills, and to form the skills of working with notebooks.

INTRODUCTION. The formation of a child's maturity depends to a large extent on beautiful writing. By writing beautifully, children have the opportunity to successfully master other subjects. The main purpose of teaching husnikhat is to develop the skills of beautiful writing by teaching the complex process of writing to young students. In the process of teaching literacy, students develop elementary skills in writing in parallel with learning to read. According to the program, students should acquire the following skills from writing:

Sitting correctly at the desk, placing the notebook correctly, marking the lines, using the pen correctly while writing, observing the border. Writing all upper and lowercase letters of the Uzbek alphabet based on a workbook or alphabet, as well as being able to connect letters to each other in words: converting printed text into written text. Writing analyzed words and two-three word sentences with the help of the teacher. Copy and write words that do not differ in pronunciation from writing and write with a dictation: check what you wrote by looking at the text and reading it with an explanation. Write a sentence from an oral story. In the process of literacy training, children write very slowly, it takes half a month to express their thoughts in writing, even with one word. Writing skills are closely related to reading skills. If the child has bad fluency, it will be difficult for him to master writing, because after the skill of syllabic reading, the skill of syllabic writing is formed. The general speech development of the child is very important for reading and writing. Later, when children's ability to express their thoughts in writing stabilizes, this ability has a positive effect on speech, thinking, and the process of expressing thoughts.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

According to the principle of analytical-synthetic sound method, the unit of reading and writing is kept. Writing letters is based on the content of teaching reading, that is, in the reading lesson, students learn the letter, read the text, and in the writing lesson, they write the

word with this letter. Teaching writing is, first of all, creating graphic skills. Each qualification is created as a result of training, skill formation and a series of exercises based on this. Graphical skill is, first of all, manual skill, this movement is primarily based on muscle power. Secondly, in the process of writing, the sound, which is the mastered unit of speech, is translated into graphic symbols, i.e. letters. This gives the writing a sense of conscious activity. Consciousness of writing requires, firstly, the correct ratio of sounds and letters, secondly, compliance with a number of graphic and orthographic rules, and thirdly, the use of writing skills to express one's thoughts and impressions. One purpose of writing is to use writing skills to express ideas. The sooner children realize this goal, the more successful and correct their written speech skills will be. In the process of literacy training, children write very slowly, it takes half a month to express their thoughts in writing, even with one word. Writing skill is inextricably linked with reading skill. If a child reads poorly, it will be difficult for him to master writing, because after the skill of reading syllabically, the skill of writing syllabically is formed. The general speech development of the child is very important for reading and writing. Later, when children's ability to express their thoughts in writing stabilizes, this ability has a positive effect on speech, thinking, and the process of expressing thoughts.

There are the following stages in the formation of graphic skills:

1. Drawing on the template of different shapes.
2. Free drawing.
3. Correct holding of writing instruments, drawing correct oblique elements, estimating length, distance, etc.

Writing letter elements, drawing short and long elements, under and over loops. Write upper and lowercase letters separately. Writing letter combinations, syllables, writing words to form the skill of writing letters correctly. The main goal of developing graphic skills is to write letters quickly and evenly without pressing them, without dividing them into elements, and to correctly place words in a line. It should be noted that during literacy training, a child imagines and thinks about how to form letters before writing them, sometimes "draws" the shape of a letter in the air, copies a sample of a letter, analyzes its composition, how to write it speaks slowly on his own: the teacher sits next to the student, holds the pen correctly and shows him how to write the letter with his hand or explains by writing it himself. In addition, the child spends a lot of physical effort on the technical side of writing. At the end of literacy training, a child can write 20 words in one lesson.

According to the decision of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, on September 2, 1993, the law "On the introduction of the Uzbek alphabet based on the Latin script" was adopted. On May 6, 1995, the law was amended. The main feature of the letters of this alphabet is that they are designed to be written without pressing and without breaking the hand. The main goal of developing graphic skills is to write letters quickly and evenly without pressing them, without dividing them into elements, and to correctly place words in a line. At school, the main writing instrument is a ballpoint pen, and chalk is used for writing on the blackboard. Different lined notebooks were used at different times to teach children to write in the period of literacy education: at first, smooth paper without lines was used, then three-lined notebooks cut with dark lines were used. A child taught to write in such a notebook was required to learn five different notebooks before graduating from primary school. Currently,

a double-lined notebook is recommended for teaching writing. It is also required that the calligraphy be suitable: from the 2nd grade, sometimes in the first grade, starting from the second half of the school year, one-line notebooks are used. Teaching them to distinguish clearly and correctly, not to forget to leave a space when writing at the beginning of a letter, educates them to be organized. In the writing class, students work with the "Notebook". It is better to have a separate notebook for practicing the letter learned in class at home.

The teacher emphasizes writing at an angle of 65 degrees while writing, and for this, the notebook is placed on the desk at an angle of 25 degrees. Orthography is derived from the Greek words "correct" and "write" and is related to the written form of the literary language. Spelling is the skill of correct spelling rules. Without knowing the orthography, the thought cannot be expressed in writing based on the norms of the literary language. Taking care of students' orthographic literacy means taking care of the accuracy of the language, the correct expression of the thoughts, and the correct interaction with people. At the same time as the formation of graphic skills in children, the ground is created for the formation of spelling skills in literacy education.

During literacy training, students:

- a) correspondence of sound and letter in words that do not differ in pronunciation and spelling;
- b) to write words separately, that is, to separate words as a unit of meaning by means of writing;
- c) to copy and write the part of the word that does not fit in the line to the next line by syllables, in this case, it is impossible to write by copying and writing the single vowel letter that forms a syllable;
- g) learn the use of initials at the beginning of the sentence, as well as in the names of people and animals in a practical way.

Copywriting, dictation and creative writing are used in the period of literacy training. They learn to check themselves. Developing students' speech and teaching them to think is one of the main tasks in writing classes.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Reading and writing is a type of speech activity. School education begins with teaching elementary reading and writing. Based on the "Alphabet", in a short time, students are taught to read and write, that is, they acquire the skills of reading and writing. Ability to perform reading and writing actions appropriately during literacy training is called reading and writing skills. This skill requires knowledge, because any skill cannot be formed without knowledge. Knowledge may not have turned into skills. For example, a child may not know the elements of the letter v, how it is placed between the writing lines, and write it in a notebook, or a student may not be able to recognize the letters and read them. In order to develop writing skills, other types of activities are also taught, such as sitting properly at the desk, holding the pen between the fingers, and placing the notebook at an angle. Reading and writing skills are being improved and turned into qualifications. An activity must be repeated several times for the formation of skills. In the writing skill, the student begins to write words and sentences without thinking about how to hold the pen and how to move it. So, the ability to read and write is a process of action without thinking. The qualification is strengthened in the next stages of training and brought to the level of automation. Reading and writing skills

ensure the successful implementation of one and the other. That is why teaching to read and writing is carried out in parallel, and this activity is practiced regularly. Therefore, in the process of teaching literacy, the child needs to read and write a lot. The Uzbek language script is a sound script, that is, a phonemic script. For each sound, for each phoneme, a special graphic form (letter) was obtained. In reading, graphic forms are converted into sounds, while in writing, on the contrary, sounds are converted into letters. Uzbek language sound system and writing. The Uzbek language script is a phonetic script. Since 1993, Latin graphics have been used as the basis for writing the Uzbek language. For each sound of speech, a corresponding graphic form was adopted. In the process of teaching literacy, the teacher should take into account the phonetic features of the Uzbek language when introducing students to sounds and letters, and teaching them to synthesize and read. Literacy is taught based on analytical-synthetic sound method. The word is divided into syllables, the desired - studied sound is separated from the syllable, analyzed, synthesized with the studied letter, and on this basis, the letter and the entire reading process are mastered. This takes into account the graphic system of the Uzbek language, the features of marking sounds in writing. It is important to take into account the following features of the graphic system of the Uzbek language when teaching literacy. Psychophysiological description of reading and writing process. Both reading and writing are complex speech activities. These processes require will, intelligence, and even physical activity from a young student.

The following are observed when teaching a young student to read:

1. The child sees one letter during reading, brings pictures to his mind to know it, remembers pictures or other letters, when he remembers, he rushes to say it, but the teacher does not allow him to say it, requires saying 'ghin. The reading process slows down until the student remembers the second letter, forgets the first one, or joins them to form a word from syllables.

2. Often the child loses the line he is reading, he has to read the letter, syllable, word again. As the student's attention expands, he begins to perceive syllables and words as a whole.

In order to successfully study, it is necessary to pay great attention to the development of students' perception, memory, thinking and speech.

Phonemic listening is an important condition for the formation of spelling skills. Therefore, it is appropriate to carry out various special exercises for the development of listening comprehension in the period of literacy training. In the process of writing, students should remember to hold the pen correctly, to place the notebook correctly, to remember the writing lines when writing a letter, to move the hand along them, how to connect the letter to the letter, how to fit the line. It should be intended that it is not. In the process of writing, the student moves the pen slowly and uncertainly on the paper, stops to write one letter and compares it with the sample, sometimes goes out of line, paints and corrects the wrong ones. Comparative and critical analysis of literacy teaching methods In the old school, reading and writing were not taught at the same time, only reading was taught before. Reading is taught by the *hijo* (syllable) method. The so-called "Hijjai ancient" method of teaching reading has continued without any changes for a long time. When literacy is taught by the sound method, the smallest part of the word, that is, speech sounds, is taken as a basis. Every sound that can

change the meaning of a word is represented by a letter in writing: it is brought to the minds of children that a new word can be formed as a result of changing, increasing or decreasing sounds in a word. In the following years, literacy is taught using the sound method. Famous methodologists (S.P. Redazubov, A.I. Voskresenskaya, K. Kasimova, Y. Abdullaev, O. Sharafiddinov, etc.) improved the teaching of literacy in the sound method. It was difficult to teach writing in the Arabic alphabet. The letters of this alphabet were written in different ways, depending on the place of use in words, which made it difficult to learn the script. That's why in many schools, children are taught to read and write, but not because most of the teachers and parents learned to read and did not know how to write. In the old school, writing was taught on plain white paper without lines, first with a thicker pencil; after the children learned to write a little, they also wrote with a reed pen, they were not allowed to write with a pen. Learning to write began with writing individual forms of letters in alphabetical order. First, the alphabet was taught, then the letters with similar shapes were divided into groups, and those without similar elements were written separately. Some teachers practiced writing the elements of some letters separately. After that, they were taught to write the letters in alphabetical order in uppercase according to the copy (this is called mufradot (sarhad): this type of writing lasted for one or two years). After that, the practice of writing letters together began. This exercise is called compound bot. The exercise of joining letters together was divided into several stages, the meaning or not of letter combinations was not taken into account at all, and how to join was practiced. In many old schools, this exercise was completed by "writing the alphabet". After the complex, the practice of copying verses, verses, and verses began. If a child knows how to write salam, he is considered to have a letter. The book "Mufradot" was used to teach writing and practice writing. All three types of exercises are given in this booklet, and in some editions, sample essays are given. In the old school, the only way to teach writing was to copy and write, as a result, the child did not develop written speech skills. This exercise made the child very bored and got used to writing without thinking. Due to the lack of creative copy writing exercises and other methods at school, even if the child has developed the skill of beautiful copy writing, he could not express his thoughts in writing, even the simplest sentences were difficult. 'r was written by mistake. Uzbek language was not taught in old schools and madrasas, as a result not only old school children, even some children who spent several years in madrasas did not know how to write their names correctly. The book "Savodi Ta'lim" by Khiva poet Shermuhammad Awazbi's son Munis (1778-1829) was used to teach correct and beautiful writing in Arabic.

CONCLUSION. To sum up, in the process of teaching elementary school students to husnikhat, first of all, it is necessary to teach teachers to husnikhat, to equip them with methods and methods. At the same time, in order to arouse interest and love for beautiful, clear and clean writing in students, first of all, the teacher should write beautifully. In 1st grade reading lessons, students are introduced to sounds and printed letters, and their speech is developed by analyzing and synthesizing sounds and letters. Such a writing class has some specific features. For example, if students use ready-to-print letters from the Alphabet book in a reading lesson, this will not be seen in a writing lesson. Each letter and its element is written by the student himself according to the sample. Therefore, teaching writing in this class requires knowledge of such concepts as: high-low, same, wide-narrow, near-far, up,

down, middle (intermediate), longer-shorter , equal, unequal distance, right-slant, left-right. Before teaching writing skills, the teacher should work with students on the above concepts. This will greatly help students to better understand the shape of letters and its movement.

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